

Relations Between Civil and Military in The Era of COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a seismic shift in the social order worldwide, profoundly altering various aspects of society. This study explores the multifaceted impact of the pandemic on global societal structure and order, encompassing mass restrictions, economic downturns, cultural transformations, and the transition to digital society. President's Decree (Keppres) No.12/2020, which declared COVID-19 a national disaster, serves as a focal point for understanding the severity and widespread implications of the crisis. Drawing upon this decree, the research examines the pandemic's toll on human lives, property, and social dynamics, highlighting its unprecedented reach and consequences. Through a comprehensive analysis, this study illuminates the far-reaching effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the fabric of society, emphasizing the urgent need for adaptive responses and resilience-building measures to mitigate its impact and foster sustainable recovery. This research aims to look for correlations in daily ongoing relationships when the Covid pandemic struck between civilians and the military in the Indonesian state. This research uses a qualitative approach methodology in the form of a literature review and in-depth interviews with one of the affected sides.

KEYWORDS : COVID-19, Military, Social Change, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the entire world's social order. Pandemics have altered the world's structure and order, affecting all nations. Pandemics are changing the structure and order of society, the impact of which is felt across the globe without exception.

The impact is profound in various aspects of the life of world society. They were starting from social spheres such as mass restrictions, economies with a declining rate of trade, and cultures with the emergence of a variety of new things, such as the shift of conventional ways of society to digital society. President's Decree (Keppres) No.12 The year 2020 on the Declaration of CoronaVirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Disaster as a National Disaster. Based on the consideration of the Presidential Decision that the disaster caused by the spread of COVID-19 has an impact with the high number of victims and loss of property, the increasingly widespread coverage of the territory as a result of the COVID-19 disaster, as well as implications on various social aspects of the community.

Based on data released by the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia, the COVID-19 pandemic situation has placed Indonesia in food instability as a result of the implemented PSBB policy, which has disrupted the processes of production, distribution and consumption of food, resulting in disruption of these three processes.¹ During the pandemic, the farming profession was most affected, as a food crisis threatened food producers. Indonesia, as an agricultural country, is significantly impacted by several data released by the Central Statistics Agency. The contribution of the agricultural sector to Indonesia's GDP continues to increase from 2019 to 2021, from 12.71% in 2019 to 13.28% in 2021. Industry Indonesian agriculture also contributes not only 13.28% of the country's real GDP but also 36% of employment and 1.34% of taxable income², which has a significant impact on the Indonesian economy.

Country	First Quarter 2020	Second Quarter 2020	Third Quarter 2020
Indonesia	2,97%	-5,32%	-3,49%
Singapore	0,7%	-42,9%	-5,8%
Malaysia	0,7%	-17,1%	-2,7%
Philippines	0,2%	-16,5%	-11,5%
Thailand	-1,8%	-12,2%	-6,4%
Vietnam	3,8%	0,4%	2,62%

Based on a comparison of data from the economic growth table for countries in the ASEAN region when the COVID-19 pandemic hit, the following indicates that the pandemic had enormous implications for a country's economy.³ The decline in a country's economy will

¹ KEMENHAN RI. (2020). Deputy Minister of Defense: The Strength of Food Security is No Less Important than the Strength of Weapons. <https://www.kemhan.go.id/2020/06/23/wamenhankekuatan-ketahanan-pangan-tak-kalahpenting-dengan-kekuatan-senjata.html>

² Central Bureau of Statistics. Results of the 2020 Social Demographic Impact of COVID-19 Survey. Retrieved October 28, 2023, from <https://www.bps.go.id/publication/2020/06/01/669cb2e8646787e52dd171c4/hasil-survei-sosial-demografi-dampak-COVID-19.html>

³ Dewi, A. A., Aulia, D., Sumunar, K. I., & Hernawati, E. (2021). The influence of COVID-19 on the economy in ASEAN countries. *JISIP (Journal of Social Sciences and Education)*, 5(3).

have implications for various branches of social factors; for example, if a country's economy declines, this will be followed by a decrease in the number of workers, which increases the country's unemployment rate, which can further have implications for increasing the crime rate in society. Observing and researching social phenomena is necessary to solve problems.

"Our success in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic cannot be separated from the big role of the TNI. The TNI has always shown professionalism in every assignment, individual ability, unit ability, utilisation of science and technology including defence equipment which has been used and deployed in carrying out every task given, "Joko Widodo, the 76th TNI's Day commemoration ceremony⁴.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the government carried out several policy efforts to handle the COVID-19 pandemic, starting with forming a Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling COVID-19, which synergised with several related ministries/institutions and regional governments. The Ministry of Defense (KEMHAN) and the Indonesian National Army (TNI) are two defence institutions also participating in efforts to overcome COVID-19. The government, together with the TNI and Polri as state institutions, have strengthened cooperation in various programs for handling COVID-19 and national economic recovery, such as vaccination programs and cash assistance distribution programs. Social assistance programs issued by the government are distributed to the community through the TNI and Polri as intermediary officers. The TNI and Polri, as components of the nation, are needed to support government policies both in the context of handling the pandemic and on other issues. These programs also have implications for the closeness of society to state institutions. The TNI and Polri, as state institutions, go directly to the community to distribute social assistance, the output of which is stronger relations between civil society and state institutions (military). It is a positive sign for the country to note that despite the negative issues, rumours, and stereotypes surrounding the Indonesian military, such as their alleged arrogance and violence towards civilians, there are indications of progress and improvement. The choice to involve the military in handling COVID-19 is also inseparable from the needs of the country's vertical structure. The TNI has adequate capabilities in various aspects, starting from information sources, human resources, and the facilities needed to distribute social assistance in logistics.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly changed how we live, interact and behave in society. One of the aspects that is greatly affected is social norms. The pandemic has triggered very complex changes in social norms, affecting how we adapt to the global health crisis. The pandemic has affected social norms, including social distancing, mask use, mobility, and social interactions. During the pandemic, societies worldwide have faced significant changes in their daily norms. Social distancing is critical in efforts to slow the spread of the virus. In order to prevent the spread of viruses, it is essential to maintain physical distance, avoid

⁴ *President Appreciates TNI's Big Role in Successful Handling of Pandemic.* (2021, October 5). State Secretariat. Retrieved October 28, 2023, from https://setneg.go.id/baca/index/presiden_apresiasi_peran_besar_tni_dalam_keberhasilan_penanganan_pandemi

crowded places, and limit face-to-face interactions to ensure the safety and well-being of everyone. These measures have significantly affected our daily lives, including work, education, and social activities. Wearing face masks has become a new normal and an essential tool to protect oneself and others from virus transmission. Wearing face masks in public areas, especially when using public transportation or when social distancing may be challenging, is highly recommended for individuals. Wearing masks not only serves as a preventative health measure but also demonstrates a sense of social responsibility towards the community. Individuals must recognise the importance of adhering to these guidelines to reduce the risk of exposure to infectious diseases. In dealing with these changes, the military has a vital role in several social contexts. The military oversees the implementation of health rules, including social distancing and the use of masks. The military is a means of logistical support in distributing masks and personal protective equipment. The military is also involved in outreach and education campaigns to ensure the public understands the importance of these changes in social norms.

The pandemic has also revealed significant disparities in the ability of individuals and communities to access quality health care. Some communities, especially in urban areas, may have better access to health facilities and medical resources compared to other groups, especially vulnerable groups such as people with low incomes, refugees, and rural communities, who already face more significant challenges in obtaining adequate care required. The pandemic has exposed significant disparities in society's access to health care, creating deep inequities in individual health experiences and outcomes. Factors such as social, economic, geographic, and racial status play a role in creating these inequalities. Individuals

in lower socio-economic groups tend to face more significant barriers to accessing quality health care. They may have financial limitations that prevent their access to expensive health services. Additionally, lack of health insurance or health coverage may also hinder their access to necessary medical care. Delays in receiving timely diagnosis, treatment and care can lead to an increased risk of health complications.

Inequality of access is also influenced by geographical factors, especially in rural or remote areas. Health facilities may be limited in these areas, with individuals having to travel long distances to receive care. Technological and informational inequality intensifies the situation by limiting access. During the pandemic, many health services switched to online platforms or telemedicine. However, individuals who do not have internet access or a communications device may need help to utilise this service.

This inequality in health access has serious consequences. Individuals who cannot access appropriate health care may face higher health risks, increased mortality rates, and long-term impacts on their well-being. Additionally, it could burden the health system with more severe cases, hinder efforts to contain the pandemic and create more profound inequalities in society. We must ensure that all individuals, regardless of their social or economic status, have equal

access to quality healthcare. This requires inclusive health policies, efforts to improve access in remote areas, and innovative solutions to overcome barriers to access. In the context of this problem, the military has a pretty important role. The military's resources, logistics, and personnel can actively support public health efforts. They can assist in setting up emergency health facilities, arranging medical transportation, and providing medical assistance such as vaccine distribution in hard-to-access areas. Apart from that, the military is also involved in education and health awareness campaigns for the public. They can spread information about preventive measures, health protocols, and the importance of vaccination. With a robust communications infrastructure, militaries can reach hard-to-reach areas, which can help reduce inequities in access to health information.

The involvement of TNI in the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) based on the command of the President, who stated in documents Presidential Decree Number 7 The year 2020 discusses How TNI was involved in tasks which were not associated with war. There are two important points regarding the involvement of the TNI in the Task Force as regulated by Presidential Decree No. 7/2020. First, the President's discretion to issue the Presidential Decree shows that there are urgent conditions that require a state decision without going through legal procedures as regulated in Law No. 34 of 2004. Second, in case of a natural disaster, the authorities must take immediate action as per the apparent rule. The Head of State, i.e., the President, holds the constitutional prerogative to oversee the implementation of new components in the OMSP⁵.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The COVID-19 pandemic, a global crisis of unprecedented proportions, triggered profound changes within societal systems. Sociologists have been instrumental in understanding and analysing the far-reaching consequences of this pandemic on various components of the social structure. This essay employs the theoretical framework of Social Systems Theory to comprehensively assess the intricate and dynamic interplay between individuals, groups, institutions, values, norms, and societal structures during the pandemic. Social Systems Theory provides a valuable framework for comprehending and addressing the challenges posed by the pandemic.

The Social Systems Theory, as a sociological concept, has been developed and refined by various scholars and thinkers over time. One of the most influential figures associated with the development of Social Systems Theory is Niklas Luhmann, a German sociologist. Luhmann's work in the latter half of the 20th century played a pivotal role in shaping this theoretical framework. Niklas Luhmann's social systems theory emphasises that society comprises various interconnected and interdependent systems, such as the economy, politics, law, education, and more. These systems interact with one another and maintain their unique

⁵Zainuddin, Z. The Role of the Indonesian National Army in Overcoming COVID-19 from a Constitutional Law Perspective. *Journal of Lex Generalis (JLS)*, 2(5), 1629-1645.

characteristics. Social Systems Theory offers a comprehensive framework for understanding the complex web of interactions and interdependencies that characterise society, particularly in the face of a global crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic. This theoretical perspective helps us make sense of how individual behaviours, group dynamics, institutional responses, and societal structures intertwine during these challenging times.

Social Systems Theory views society as a complex and interconnected web of elements where individual actions influence and are influenced by the larger social context. At its core, the theory recognises the agency of individuals and their collective interactions within groups. These groups, or subsystems, are guided by shared norms and values, and they function within larger societal structures. The theory also considers how institutions and organisations uphold these structures and maintain social equilibrium. In essence, it recognises the symbiotic relationship between individual actors, their immediate social circles, and the overarching society, emphasising the systemic nature of social phenomena. Social Systems Theory consists of several interrelated components.

First and foremost, it recognises the role of individuals as the building blocks of society. These individuals form various groups or subsystems within society, such as families, communities, workplaces, and educational institutions. Each group adheres to norms and values that define their collective identity and behaviour. These shared norms and values are an essential part of the theory, as they provide cohesion and structure to social groups. Furthermore, institutions and organisations, such as governments, healthcare systems, and religious entities, serve as pillars that support societal structures and maintain order.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, social systems theory provides certain advantages for diagnosing modern civilisation. The ability of social systems theory to characterise a critical condition beyond common sense ideas of crisis and catastrophe is a benefit. Indeed, they are worrisome descriptions that need immediate action but cannot articulate society's intricacies⁶. Social systems theory provides a second-order observation⁷ of morality, which implies that it is not concerned with identifying who is good or evil but rather with observing the conditions and effects of using the moral code's unique differentiation. In this context, "second-order observation" suggests that one does not identify with morally oriented observers under the banner of the notion of the good but instead asks what they see and do not perceive while watching within the framework of the moral code. Society's tangible communication activities, based on differences in perception and explanation of reality, shape the social systems theory viewpoint. It does not claim exclusive access to reality, but it does provide an observation of blind spots that would otherwise go unnoticed. It acts "as a vehicle for observing morally oriented communications and destroys, with or without

⁶Luhmann, N. (1984), "The self-description of society: crisis fashion and sociological theory", *International Journal of Comparative Sociology*, Vol. 25 Nos 1-2, pp. 59-72.

⁷Luhmann, N. (2002b), "The cognitive program of constructivism and the reality that remains unknown", in Luhmann, N. (Ed.), *Theories of Distinction: Redescribing the Descriptions of Modernity*, Stanford University Press, Stanford, CA, pp. 128-152

intention, the immediacy of moral evidence⁸."

Employing Social Systems Theory, we can analyse the multifaceted impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on various aspects of society. Individual behaviour, such as social distancing and mask-wearing, has become crucial in curbing the spread of the virus. These actions, influenced by government policies and health guidelines, reveal the dynamic relationship between individual agency and institutional authority. The changes in group dynamics, from the isolation of families to the adaptation of remote work within organisations, highlight the adaptability of social subsystems. Institutions like healthcare systems have faced immense challenges, necessitating rapid adjustments and resource allocation to maintain societal well-being. The theory underlines the intricate interconnectedness and interactions within and between these components. It posits that individual actions can have far-reaching consequences, impacting not only their immediate social environment but also the broader social structures.

Conversely, societal institutions and organisations can influence the behaviours and values of individuals and groups. The COVID-19 pandemic is a prime example of how these interactions manifest. The actions of individuals, such as compliance with public health measures, affect the spread of the virus and the strain on healthcare systems. Governments and public health organisations simultaneously establish guidelines and regulations that reshape individual behaviours and societal norms.

THE ANALYSIS

Individual acts are essential within the more excellent society environment, according to Social Systems Theory. Analysing the pandemic from this angle allows us to delve into the complexities of individual agency and compliance. How have individuals responded to the epidemic, driven by cultural standards and government directives? Within the realm of Social Systems Theory, the examination of individual agency and compliance during the COVID-19 pandemic provides a crucial lens for understanding the dynamic interplay between individual actions and broader societal structures.

The interview data from Raphael, a 19-year-old male, provides insights into the role of the military during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. Raphael highlights the direct involvement of the military, particularly the TNI (Tentara Nasional Indonesia), in collaboration with the community. The military played a crucial role in health-related activities, such as operating health posts, assisting in clinics and hospitals, and providing vaccination education. Raphael's interview opens a gateway to a more profound exploration of the military's involvement during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia, delving into the intricacies of public perception, political maneuvering, and the evolving role of the military in both crisis response and civilian affairs. The recognition of the military's adaptability and

⁸Luhmann, N. (1992a), "The code of the moral", *Cardozo Law Review*, Vol. 14, pp. 995-1009.

direct impact in crisis management, particularly in the challenging context of a health emergency, prompts a broader discussion about the role of the military beyond its traditional security functions. The ability to efficiently distribute vaccines to remote areas showcases a unique set of skills and resources that the military possesses. This prompts reflection on the potential dual nature of the military as both a security apparatus and a force capable of contributing significantly to public welfare.

“Menurut saya pribadi peran militer ketika penanganan pandemi kemarin telah memperkuat people trust kepada pemerintah. Namun, terkadang masih saja dimasuki issue tentang penggelapan dana seperti bisnis vaksin, minyak, dll. Hal tersebut membuat sedikit penurunan people trust terhadap pemerintah. Biasanya hal tersebut memang sudah disusun terstruktur by design yang berasal dari pihak-pihak berlawanan dengan paham pemerintah semisal dari pihak oposisi pemerintah.”

The acknowledgment of persistent issues, such as alleged fund mismanagement, introduces an element of skepticism and highlights the complex nature of public discourse during crises. Raphael's insight into the strategic crafting of allegations by opposition parties underlines the political dimensions of the military's involvement. It encourages a critical examination of how information is disseminated and received by the public, emphasizing the need for media literacy and discernment in navigating narratives during times of crisis. The paradoxical impact on public trust, where the military's active role strengthens trust while allegations simultaneously erode it, unveils a delicate balance. This duality underscores the fragility of public perception and the challenges associated with maintaining trust in institutions amid external pressures. It also prompts considerations about the role of transparency and accountability in mitigating the potential erosion of public trust, particularly when facing complex challenges such as a global pandemic.

“Akan tetapi, dengan munculnya kasus dimana militer dapat menempati posisi pekerjaan masyarakat sipil seperti misal PNS, kepala daerah, dan semacamnya. Hal ini menurut saya pribadi adalah sebuah simbol kemunduran, kembali lagi ke era orde baru yang mana hal tersebut mengurangi tingkat kepercayaan masyarakat yang telah cukup bagus di zaman penanganan pandemi COVID-19 kemarin.”

Raphael's observation of the military's active and visible engagement compared to civilian entities underscores the potential implications of such prominence. While it contributes to increased trust in state institutions, questions arise about the militarization of civilian spheres and the potential long-term consequences on democratic principles. This prompts a nuanced exploration of the boundaries between military and civilian domains, emphasizing the importance of preserving democratic values while recognizing the need for effective crisis management.

The pandemic has highlighted several elements that influence individual agency. Personal views, values, and risk perceptions are among the essential drivers. Those who prioritise public health and believe they have a moral duty to protect the weak, for example, are more inclined to follow public health norms. Scepticism, disinformation, and suspicion of authority,

on the other hand, can stymie individual agency, leading to noncompliance with prescribed actions. Compliance with public health measures during the pandemic was also firmly ingrained in societal norms and beliefs. Individuals' conduct within their social groups and communities are governed by these norms, usually affected by collective values. As a result, compliance is more than simply a personal act; it reflects societal and cultural dynamics. The pandemic has demonstrated the importance of social norms and peer pressure in moulding compliance. Individuals are more inclined to follow guidelines if they see their friends, family members, and colleagues doing so. Individuals may become resistant to compliance if they believe that the bulk of their social network opposes public health policies.

The pandemic acted as a disruptive force in a world accustomed to a degree of predictability in social interactions, challenging the established norms and values that governed how various groups functioned. Families, communities, workplaces, and social circles were transitioning as they adjusted to the new reality. This adaptation, informed by collective norms and values, provides an intriguing vista for investigation. The norms that had previously guided these groups transformed. The concept of family has been redefined, with new norms emerging around ideas such as social distancing within households and homeschooling. Communities that used to thrive on close-knit interactions have seen norms shift towards neighbourly support for vulnerable members and new guidelines for public gatherings. Remote work has become more common, transforming traditional office dynamics and dress codes. These shifts in group norms offer a fascinating glimpse into the adaptability of social systems.

The intricate interplay between the pandemic's various components is also one of the fundamental aspects of the Social Systems Theory applied to it. Individual actions, according to the theory, are deeply entwined with the behaviours and expectations of the societal systems that surround them. These interactions reveal a wealth of information about the crisis's complexities. Government policies, media messaging, and peer influences can influence individual actions such as mask-wearing, social distancing, and vaccine hesitancy. The power dynamics between individuals and institutions are exposed, emphasising the importance of trust and legitimacy in shaping collective behaviour. Individual behaviours, in turn, influence how these institutions function. Compliance or resistance to public health measures can strain healthcare systems, influence the need for policy changes, and, ultimately, impact societal well-being. These feedback loops demonstrate the dynamic nature of the relationships within the societal system, where small changes in one component can have a cascading effect on the entire system.

THE CONCLUSION

The intricate interplay between military and civilian life amid the COVID-19 pandemic unravels a complex tapestry of dynamic relationships, echoing the profound insights articulated by Raphael. Beyond conventional security roles, the crisis has illuminated the

military's multifaceted capacities in addressing not only traditional threats but also navigating the complexities of major public health crises. The pandemic serves as a crucible, demanding a recalibration of our understanding of the military's role, extending beyond its historical purview. As elucidated by Raphael, the military's extensive involvement in societal affairs during health emergencies encompasses not only a rapid response to crises but also the enforcement of public health measures and the provision of indispensable logistical support in tandem with civilian authorities. This expanded role prompts a nuanced reconsideration of the dichotomy between national security imperatives and the imperative to safeguard public health, urging a holistic and interconnected approach to crisis management.

Raphael's observations underscore the pivotal role of trust, transparency, and accountability in shaping military-civilian relations, particularly during times of crisis. The allegations of fund mismanagement, as highlighted, underscore the fragility of public trust. In an era where citizens seek guidance and support from the military, the cooperative response hinges upon a delicate balance of trust and a clear demonstration of commitment to the collective well-being. The military's influence extends beyond traditional realms, becoming integral to societal psychological well-being and the maintenance of social stability. In the evolving landscape of the pandemic, Raphael's insights serve as a sophisticated framework for navigating the intricate dynamics between the military and civilian spheres. The symbiotic relationship between these entities becomes more apparent, emphasizing the interconnectedness that underpins the resilience of nations in the face of multifaceted challenges. These nuanced dynamics transcend immediate crisis management, offering profound lessons that can inform future strategies, wherein military institutions collaborate with civilian entities in a more integrated and mutually beneficial manner.

As societies grapple with the ever-shifting challenges presented by the pandemic, the lessons gleaned from Raphael's perspective become invaluable pillars for resilience. These insights extend beyond crisis management, providing guidance on fortifying the bonds of trust between military institutions and the societies they serve. In essence, Raphael's observations offer a compass for navigating the complex intersections of military and civilian life, laying the groundwork for strategies that promote resilience, unity, and adaptability in the face of unprecedented challenges on a global scale.

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